

REIMAGING PRIMARY SCIENCE CURRICULUM AS ADVENTURE FOR NURTURING SCIENTIFIC REASONING

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Abstract

The importance of raising a generation of scientific thinkers and problem-solvers for the 21st century workspace has been severally stressed. This paper notes that the pursuit should begin at the primary science classroom. It proposes that science learning at that stage should be framed as adventure, leveraging on children's innate curiosity to enhance inquiry, and evidence-based thinking instead of exposition and memorization. It highlights modern pedagogical perspectives such as inquiry-based learning, playful exploration, dialogic teaching, and context relevant instruction as strategic in developing these competencies. The paper disparages exam-oriented systems, limited teacher preparedness, resource constraints, and inequities as inimical to early scientific reasoning acquisition. It proposes assessment system reforms, teacher continuous professional development, and learners' everyday contexts to boost inquiry by a re-envisioning of primary science as an engaging, exploratory adventure for laying solid foundation for scientific reasoning and effective participation in future scientific workspace.

Keywords: Primary science; Scientific reasoning; curriculum as adventure; science learning; Science education; science curriculum

Introduction

Humans are naturally adventurous. This characteristic is often very distinct among children who in their quest to understand nature, ask numerous questions and explore their environment. Can you imagine why some children destroy electronic gadgets without intent to do so, rip open expensive household equipment and in some cases get injured in the process? Consider what goes on in the mind of an eight-year-old struggling to understand why some organisms are so small and others so large, why and how organisms as small as ants can build magnificent anthills, why grasshoppers on the school field keep hopping away with each attempt to catch them, and why a particular piece of metal cannot pass through a loop when it is hot but does so when cool. Children struggle to understand these moments often considered as play but are profound attempts to make sense of the world around them leveraging

on their innate curiosity. Angkur (2025) has stated that these instincts naturally equip children with tendencies for nurturing reasoning, culminating in children's early learning of science through play. However, oftentimes, primary science teachers ignore these innate science instincts and sparks and focus on content exposition of what children are supposed to discover by themselves (Raven & Wenner, 2022; Fridman et al. 2020; Delserieys & Kampeza, 2025).

Skills associated with scientific reasoning include observing, asking questions no matter how senseless they may seem, predicting, designing simple experiments, and evaluating evidence. These skills though rudimentary in children, are both foundational and fundamental to science learning at all levels. Their acquisition is not only necessary for science learning but also of immense importance in our rapidly changing complex world that is facing challenges as climate change,

pandemics, misinformation, insecurity, wars, technological upsurge and international competitiveness. Only children who are keen observers, solution seekers, and thinkers from an early age are better equipped to engage, evaluate, adapt and act appropriately. This opinion piece elucidates (1) the nature of science reasoning and why it matters in science learning (2) modern viewpoints about how children develop reasoning skills (3) gaps and challenges in primary science curricula and teaching and (4) view that primary science curriculum should be an “adventure” that deliberately scaffolds reasoning, foster curiosity, and build habits of inquiry in ways that conform to human natural instincts.

Nature of Science Reasoning in Young Learners and Does It Matter?

Studies have noted the incoherence in the perception about of scientific reasoning, often with inadvertent omission of the procedural and epistemic components, as well as its instructional and assessment procedures (Kind & Osborne, 2017; Osborne, 2013; Bao et al, 2023). Scientific reasoning is a group of mental skills that help people understand how things work in nature. It is a way of using logic and reasoning to find proof in order to learn about the natural world. Scientific reasoning also consists of skills which learners need to observe, make guesses, predict events, generate data, and carry out investigations from which they draw conclusions. This series of activities enable the learners to review previous evidence or adapt them to new knowledge (Boa et al., 2022; Piekny & Maehler, 2013; Schlatter et al., 2021, 2022; Achiaw & Owusu, 2023). Children learn these skills in no particular order. They are often exhibited at different times and at different speeds and magnitude based on a child’s personal characteristics. Research shows that while the ability to experiment (hands-on, trial and error, observe) improves through primary years,

generating hypotheses and evaluating data are often slower and requires scaffolding to achieve (Schlatter et al., 2021).

Why are scientific reasoning skills necessary for learning science? Scientific reasoning is directly related to how well you can reason and how well you can understand things, both of which are important for critical thinking and doing well in life. When kids are not only told facts, but taught to ask "why" and "how do," they learn better and remember things better with fewer mistakes. This makes them able to transfer knowledge and skills to new and related situations (Angkur, 2025; Schlatter, 2021, 2022; Jirout, 2020; Moemeke, 2019). Also, children that reason scientifically are acritical thinkers and are likely to be good problem-solvers adaptable to the 21st-century workplace. As the world becomes more globalized, digitalized, flooded by artificial intelligence and technological innovations, some of which result in misinformation, individuals require skills for rational thought early in life for significant decision-making. These decisions may have implications for health, the environment, technology, safety, food, or even finance. A child who engages in evidence-based reasoning is better prepared to critically assess assertions (Moemeke, 2019, 2023; Jirout, 2020). Also, learning how to think critically at a young age helps individuals to learn all through life. The more kids ask questions, explore, and develop their intellectual curiosity from an early age, the more confident they will be in doing so.

Early acquisition of reasoning skills has also been linked to success in science and mathematics in later years (Osterhaus & Koerber, 2025). When science learning at the primary school level intentionally focuses on their development, a solid foundation is laid for future advanced science learning and interest, both of which support success in science-related fields and careers later in life (Zhou et al, 2021; Mayer et al., 2014; Bao et al., 2023; Schletter et al.,

2020). Early acquisition of scientific reasoning skills further enhance curiosity, motivate learner for further learning with a growth mindset that perseveres in the face of challenges. (Sudhakar, 2025; Jirout, 2020).

Understanding Science Reasoning in Young Learners

Changing that curiosity into scientific reasoning is a process that includes many steps, supports, and situations that work together. Schlatter et al.

(2021), Osterhaus et al. (2023), and Lazonder et al. (2020) assert that the development of scientific reasoning skills commences at a significantly earlier age than commonly presumed, typically between 5 to 7 years. Research delineates essential characteristics regarding the nature, development, and determinants of scientific reasoning in young learners, including

- Conducting experiments and designing investigations that include establishing tests, managing variables, and examining causality. Studies indicate that while these skills are inherently present in all individuals, they can be enhanced and fortified through focused instruction, practice, and conducive learning environments (Osterhaus et al., 2016; Tytler & Peterson, 2003). While experimenting and designing investigations are central to primary school scientific reasoning, they require explicit teaching, practice, and supportive contexts. This is because mastery of controlling variables and understanding cause-and-effect relationships develops over time and is influenced by cognitive, social, and instructional factors. Effective science education should integrate hands-on, inquiry-based, and research-driven approaches to foster these essential skills in young learners.

Analyzing data and evidence by looking at what was collected, finding patterns,

and figuring out which evidence is conclusive and which is not.

- Hypothesizing or predicting is when you make guesses or statements about what might happen in the future based on what you already know and have seen (Schlatter et al., 2021; Osterhaus et al., 2020; Widyaningsih & 2020; Yi-Yi, & Mingming, 2018).
- Mechanistic reasoning entails elucidating causal mechanisms and factors that contribute to an event by discerning and correlating occurrences with their underlying causes, the entities involved, and their interactions across various levels (Ryan et al., 2023; Berg & Hultén, 2023; Russ et al., 2008; Ladachart et al., 2021). This reasoning is sporadic, contextually contingent, and reliant on the presence of inquiry opportunities, which can be cultivated through deliberate curriculum design and classroom methodologies. Berg and Hultén (2024) studied 9- to 10-year-old third graders who used model-based inquiry to learn about thermal expansion. They found that young primary pupils can use mechanistic reasoning when the learning environment encourages modeling, observation, and explanation. They could switch between different levels of representation (from big-picture observations to ideas about particles) and make connections between causes, even when the teacher did not clearly define them technically.
- Employing epistemic thinking to understand that scientific knowledge is provisional, grounded in evidence, but without of absolute truth, yet influenced by frameworks and interpretations (Osterhaus, 2017; Mayer et al., 2014).

Developmental Patterns and Variability among Children Learning Science

The rate, speed and ease with which children of the same age develop scientific reasoning vary widely. Some children may

excel in specific abilities, such as experimentation, yet may underperform in others, including hypothesis formulation, data appraisal, and conclusion drawing (Chionas & Emvalotis, 2025; Schlatter et al. 2021; Oslington, 2021). Lazonder et al. (2021) observed that scientific thinking is dynamic, with children aged 5 to 10 exhibiting development in several subskills. Research indicates that significant factors influencing this developmental trajectory encompass overall cognitive aptitude, familial environment, and the epistemic beliefs of parents. (Osterhaus, & Koerber, 2024; Lin et al. 2024; Junge et al. 2021; Bae et al. 2023). Research shows that when provided appropriate scaffolds, such as clear representations, teacher guidance, and chances to test models and review explanations, young children in early primary school level can start reasoning about cause-and-effect systems (Booth et al. 2020). Parental expectations for success in science (Thomas & Strunk, 2017) and science engagement (Dominke et al., 2025; Pinneo & Nolen, 2024) are found to be strongly correlated with parental emotional-motivational support.

Enablers of scientific reasoning development in children

Literature indicates several support and contextual factors as facilitating scientific skill development in children:

1. Use of representations and multimodality: Representations (e.g. diagrams, models, particle visuals) help children move between what they observe and what is underneath (cause). Also changing presentation media (speech, drawing, physical models) supports understanding by enabling children shifted between macro and sub-micro explanations as the modalities are shifted (Louca & Zacharia, 2024; Nichols et al. 2025; McLure et al 2021). Facilitators of children's development of scientific reasoning.

2. Instructional design (Model-Based and Inquiry Learning): Classrooms that use inquiry or model-based learning where students are guided to build models, test them, revise them, and explain, produce stronger reasoning outcomes than more didactic or lecture-style approaches (Penelitian et al. 2025; Sutiani et al. 2021; Moemeke et al. 2025). One typical instance is when science students in elementary school investigate thermal expansion to determine why metal balls can pass through a ring while they are cool but not when they are heated. Therefore, during inquiry-based research, the development of scientific thinking is strongly aided by opportunities for introspection, peer collaboration, and experimentation.
3. Scaffolding and working examples: Research shows that providing worked examples is beneficial for more fundamental process skills like conducting observation (Al-Barakat et al. 2025; Lechner et al. 2024; Chen et al. 2023).
4. Cognitive abilities, language, and reading comprehension. Reasoning is not an isolated process. Children's ability to interpret data, comprehend hypotheses, or assess results is correlated with skills like reading comprehension and numeracy. Of additional importance is executive functioning, which includes working memory and attention.

Implications for Curriculum and Teaching

- The following are lessons for educators, curriculum designers, and policy makers: Progressive scaffolding should be incorporated into curricula, with an initial focus on observation and basic experimentation followed by the gradual introduction of hypothesis development, evaluation, evidence reasoning, and mechanical thinking.

- Consistent and regular development requires regular, well-planned inquiry experiences. Teachers must be trained and assisted in using model-based inquiry, guiding students as they work across representational levels, identifying misconceptions, and providing a safe space for failure when it occurs.
 - Learners are assisted in transitioning from simple to more abstract reasoning through the use of concrete models, multimodal representations, and practical examples.
 - Reasoning process should be valued in assessment systems rather than merely memory. Incorporate tests of thinking abilities, confidence, and attitude to identify misconceptions.
 - Engage parents and community: given that parental epistemic beliefs influence development, curricula or interventions might include components that reach families, helping them understand what science reasoning is, and encourage discourse at home.
- “why do puddles on the road on a sunny day disappear as you approach it”? “Why do some foods cuddles with heat”? “Why does shadow change size and direction as the day goes by”? This can be enhanced with keeping of children’s question journals and recordings for future inquiry activities. Thus, connecting science lessons and instruction to children’s real contexts, not only fosters reasoning but strengthens abstract thinking using familiar experiences (Cotič et al. 2020; Wang & Chen, 2025)

Useful Techniques for Teachers to Encourage Young Students to Reason Scientifically

To support children's development, educators must first understand how they reason scientifically. Transforming classrooms from a place where students memorize science facts to one where procedural science teaching and learning are promoted is crucial. Even in environments with limited resources, primary science teachers may help children to reason by using practical ideas and activities. These insights consist of

- The deliberate application of inquiry-based learning (IBL) as the first choice teaching method. Using a set of basic instruments and equipment in a "predict-observe-explain" cycle, may entail straightforward but thought-provoking out-of-laboratory investigations (Moemeke, 2024; De La Peña, & Maatubang, 2025). By structuring hypothesis, evidence use, and conclusion-making, asking students what they think will happen (prediction), allowing them to observe (observation), and then asking them to explain why (explanation) unifies scientific reasoning. Even when teachers are still inexperienced with inquiry, Sam (2024) and Dah et al. (2024) note that inquiry-based techniques greatly enhance motivation and reasoning abilities.
- Develop challenging subskills (evaluating evidence and formulating hypotheses). According to research, children's most difficult subskills are hypothesizing and evaluating evidence (Piekny & Maehler, 2013). In order to lessen cognitive overload and encourage students to connect predictions with explanations, teachers should concentrate on their achievement by asking for predictions and using prompts and sentence-starters like "I think ___will happen because ___."

- Moving from what they see (macro level) to invisible processes (micro level) is frequently difficult for children. Drawings, role plays, and use of instructional items are examples of models that frequently aid in bridging this gap. Mechanistic reasoning is embedded through this such representations (Adbo & Carulla, 2020; Louca & Zacharia, 2024; Charalampopoulou et al., 2023; Berg & Hultén, 2023).
- Putting more emphasis on the thought process than the accuracy of the responses. Giving students the freedom to speak and express their ideas reveals their cognitive processes and makes it feasible to address misconceptions.
- Reasoning should be given more weight in assessments of science learning outcomes. Instead than focusing on recall, evaluation tools should be made to provoke thought.
- Schools should help parents comprehend what scientific reasoning entails because children's reasoning is predicted by their parents' epistemic beliefs (Belenky et al., 2024). Parents are often included in school science programs where kids' scientific creations are displayed.

Primary Science as Adventure

Primary science is an exploration of the unknown rather than just a subject. Every stone that is overturned, every insect that is seen, every drop of water that is investigated, and even the natural occurrence of day and night are full of questions for young learners that are comparable to inquiry and subsequent discovery. When kids approach science as an adventure, it stops being a list of facts to learn by heart and instead becomes a narrative in which they are the characters.

The three components that propel scientific thinking are curiosity, challenge, and discovery. These are also indispensable in every adventure. Curiosity is a natural

beginning place for young learners. When teachers recognize children's quest to satisfy their curiosity, they use these questions as the compass for science learning. Studies emphasize that curiosity-driven activities strengthen reasoning and motivation to learn (Chinonso & Mokiwa, 2022). Modern science education emphasizes that children should not only know what scientists have discovered but also experience, replicate, model and extend how scientists think and explore. This progressive shift turns the primary science learning into a series of small adventures guided by teachers but fueled by the children's own distinctive power of wonder, shaping reasoning skills along the way. The teachers' skillfulness in fostering adventure thus lies in noticing patterns in children's reasoning, leading them to test their naive ideas, and guiding them to piece them together to make coherent explanations. As Reiss (2023) explains that when science is embedded in everyday contexts, learners become active discoverers rather than passive recipients of knowledge.

In addition, every adventure must host some challenges to be meaningful. In science, these challenges come in the form of puzzles, anomalies, or unexpected results. If every prediction turns out "Correct", then there would be no need for reasoning but when a potted plant withers while others grow healthily or an experiment yields a surprising outcome, an opportunity to think harder and deeper to determine cause is created as the child strives to find an explanation. In this way, children learn resilience, persistence, and evidence-based reasoning which are key competencies for science learning. According to Reiss (2023), helping learners embrace uncertainty and challenges foster long-term positive attitudes towards science.

Reimagining science learning as adventure in the primary school also reframes the teacher's role in science learning and curriculum designing. The role

of the teacher necessarily transforms from being a deliverer of knowledge to a guide leading a team on an expedition. This involves crafting science lessons as in a fun island but laden with experiences that create understanding instead of search for correct answers. Studies highlight that children engage more deeply when science activities evoke wonder and exploration rather than repetition (Chinonso & Mokiwa, 2022; Reiss, 2023). Science as adventure helps bridge the gap between prescribed curriculum objectives and children's innate curiosity and interest. This sense of ownership builds confidence, resilience, and persistence which are traits crucial for lifelong learning in science even after school.

An interesting feature of adventure is its flexibility and playfulness. The playful nature of adventure allows children to imagine, test, and re-test ideas without fear of failure. For example, when experimenting with magnets, children might first treat it like a game, testing what it attracts and what it does not attract. But as the teacher prompts them to organize observations, ask why, and form predictions, the play translates to inquiry. Chinonso and Mokiwa (2022) argue that blending play with structured inquiry not only sustains engagement but also develops deeper scientific reasoning from an early age.

Contrary to conventional beliefs, teaching science adventurously does not require high-cost equipment. Simplest tools such as a bowl of water with lather of soap under the sun, magnifying glass, a plastic bottle, chalk, assorted leaves, roots and stems or even learners' bodies can serve as instruments of discovery. Simple balloons, children's kites and even a kettle of boiled water or use shadows on the playground can be used to explore diverse natural phenomena. It is however important to note that the quality of the adventure does not necessarily depend on the complexity of the materials used but on how the teacher

frames the simple things. As the Royal Society of Chemistry (2023) highlights, science reasoning develops best when learners become actively involved in doing science even with

The procedural and destination-bound nature of adventure is another characteristic. Teachers must constantly push students to express predictions, defend concepts, and share conclusions as they embark on scientific adventures with the goal of unlocking thinking. This reinforces the idea that science is not just about right answers but also about how we arrive at them by making thinking more concrete, palpable, and collaborative. Additionally, it transforms young students become evidence-seekers with the mindset to investigate rather than absorb information.

Schools can change children's attitudes toward learning from dreading failure, obstacles, and mistakes to accepting mistakes as an essential component of an inquiry challenge by reimagining science as an adventure. limited resources. Instead of passively listening, they actively explore, test, and revise their ideas. In this way, the primary science curriculum becomes a hub for cultivating scientific ways of thinking anchored in curiosity, evidence, and persistence.

Impediments to effective scientific reasoning development in primary school learners

Even with strong support, navigating scientific reasoning in young science learners can be difficult due to their deficiency in formal operational reasoning structures. Children may be able to observe, conduct experiments, and appropriately report their findings, but they are often challenges hypothesizing. Some even struggle to properly assess evidence and make inferences.

In addition, instead of using logic, they frequently compare novel phenomena to well-known instances. This innate inclination could be caused by the enormous

mental strain that comes with thinking, which makes it difficult to rationalize when phenomena deviate from predicted prototypes.

Notably too, children are often exhibit flaws in thinking and reasoning due to poor engagement with reasoning activities. Misconceptions of scientific knowledge and everyday community myths and pseudo-scientific thoughts prevalent in the community but are not in alignment with scientific disciplinary thinking also impede science reasoning development especially in non-western cultures.

Teachers' Challenges in Nurturing Scientific Reasoning in Primary Science

The reality of classrooms often presents obstacles to teachers while guiding learners in science. Teachers face challenges that can make it difficult to move from aspiration to practice. Recognizing these challenges is essential, not to discourage innovation, but to ensure strategies are realistic, supportive, and sustainable.

1. The regularity, quality, and sufficiency of teacher preparation and confidence. Many elementary school instructors are not well-versed in science pedagogy, particularly when it comes to employing inquiry-based methods. Even when training is offered, it is frequently theoretical, leaving educators confused of how to put it into reality. As a result, instructors frequently justify avoiding reasoning-based exercises in the classroom by citing low confidence, time constraints, and a lack of pedagogical resources (RSC, 2023).
2. In many schools, especially those in low-income or rural areas, resource constraints are a daily reality. Simple experiment kits, measuring instruments, and magnifying glasses are examples of fundamental science supplies that teachers might not have.

While modern perspectives emphasize that reasoning can be nurtured even with

everyday materials, the absence of supportive infrastructure can still restrict teachers' creativity and learners' opportunities for hands-on inquiry (Chinonso & Mokiwa, 2022).

3. Primary school curricula often have many subjects competing for the limited number of school hours. Such crowded curriculum does not create room for pedagogic flexibility and creativity. This limits the time the teachers may allow for extended investigations or dialogue-based lessons. Fleer and Van Oers (2022) argue that developing reasoning is inherently a slower process, requiring space for questioning, mistakes, and reflection, luxuries that exam-oriented schedules rarely permit. In many education systems especially in developing nations, assessment remains heavily exam-driven, prioritizing factual recall over reasoning processes. Teachers often feel pressured to "teach to the test," narrowing their lessons to memorization rather than exploration. As Reiss (2023) points out, when success is defined primarily by correct answers in high-stakes assessments, curiosity and inquiry are sidelined. This misalignment between curriculum ideals and assessment realities is a critical barrier to nurturing reasoning. Learners' experiences are also influenced by parents' and teachers' attitudes toward science. Students soon adopt the same perspective if science is perceived as a discipline of "facts to memorize" rather than "questions to explore." Parental epistemic beliefs have a significant impact on children's reasoning, according to research, therefore efforts to foster inquiry in the classroom may be compromised if they are not supported at home (Belenky et al., 2024). Thus, altering societal perceptions of what it means to "do science" is an important but difficult task.
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6. Both the subject matter of science and the language of education are difficult for young primary science learners and their teachers to comprehend. This constitutes additional challenge to the young science learner and may stifle scientific reasoning before it has a chance to flourish.
7. Lastly, not every student has the same chance to develop their thinking skills. Socioeconomic disparities, rural-urban differences, and gender norms and race influence who participates in science and how. In certain situations, girls are still discouraged from investigating scientific concepts, and students from underprivileged homes frequently lack access to extracurricular inquiry opportunities. In such situations of inequality, fostering scientific reasoning may suffer the risk of becoming a privilege rather than a right.

Recommendations and Future Directions

There is no denying the difficulties in fostering scientific reasoning in elementary science through an adventure-based curriculum, but these difficulties are not insurmountable. They offer communities, educators, and legislators a compelling call to rethink elementary science as a dynamic journey that prepares kids to think critically, ask questions, and take action in a world that is constantly changing. Deliberate action is required to do this.

It is necessary to establish assessment instruments that assess children's inquiries, predictions, thoughts, and explanations for events. Portfolios, thinking journals, and group studies that assess both the process and product aspects of research should be among these evaluation techniques. Teachers training must go beyond content delivery and equip teachers with practical strategies for inquiry, dialogue, and reasoning scaffolds. Such training should be regular, continuous along with provision of activity banks and

low-cost experiment kits for resource limited schools.

Science is demystified when kids encounter is in naturally occurring events that are context-specific. Science becomes less abstract and more relatable to kids when they encounter it in everyday situations. Teachers should use local examples and make learners observe science at play in their local environments.

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